

Coping Strategies for Work-Related Stress Affecting Performance of Administration Police Service in Narok County, Kenya

Chimwaga Mongo

School of Arts and Social Sciences, Masai Mara University, Kenya

Abstract: Work-related stress is a pattern of reactions that occurs when workers are presented with work demands that are not matched to their knowledge, skills or abilities, and which challenge their ability to cope. These demands may be related to time pressure or the amount of work (quantitative demands), or may refer to the difficulty of the work (cognitive demands) or the empathy required (emotional demands), or even to the inability to show one's emotions at work. The main objective of this study was to establish the coping strategies for work-related stress on the performance of the Administration Police service in Narok County, Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Data was collected using structured questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study found that personal sphere sources of work-related stress were prevalent meaning much more is needed to ensure personal well being of Administration Police officers in Narok County. It was found that delegation of responsibilities and taking refuge in family friends were the leading options of coping with stress among Administration police officers in Narok County. Other significant coping strategies include visits to the chaplain often to cope with work related stressful situations and exercising regularly and maintaining a sense of humor respectively as the main ways of coping of with stress. Going to church, limited taking of alcohol, meditating, smoking, eating more sensibly, getting a massage and using other drugs were other ways adopted by officers to cope with stress. However, the findings revealed that, despite the coping strategies often used such as provision of leave/pass leave, disciplinary mechanisms and hospitalization for chronic stress cases, the occurrence of work related stress was still high. It can be concluded thus from these findings that the coping strategies currently in place are not adequate to prevent and manage effects of work related stress.

Key Terms: Coping Strategies, Stress, Performance

I. Introduction

Work-related stress is a pattern of reactions that occurs when workers are presented with work demands that are not matched to their knowledge, skills or abilities, and which challenge their ability to cope [1]. These demands may be related to time pressure or the amount of work (quantitative demands), or may refer to the difficulty of the work (cognitive demands) or the empathy required (emotional demands), or even to the inability to show one's emotions at work. Demands may also be physical, i.e. high demands in the area of dynamic and static loads. When the worker perceives an imbalance between demands and environmental or personal resources, this can cause a number of possible reactions. These may include physiological responses (increase in heart rate, blood pressure, hyperventilation), emotional responses (feeling nervous or irritated), cognitive responses (reduced attention and perception, forgetfulness), and behavioral reactions (e.g. aggressive, impulsive behavior, making mistakes). When people are in a state of stress, they often feel concerned, less vigilant and less efficient in performing tasks. [2], links causes of work stress to the work itself, including; increasing demands, less freedom to control one's work, and also to the person, (insufficient capacity to cope with time pressures. He further attributes the occurrence of stress to various circumstances, but argues that it is particularly strong when a person's ability to control the demands of work is threatened. The stressful experience may be intensified if no help is available from colleagues or supervisors at work. [1], on the other hand argues that when demands exceed one's abilities and knowledge, but one is able to perceive this as an opportunity to work towards achieving a state of balance, a situation of learning and development may arise.

Both [3] and [4] established that the body possesses an internal mechanism to maintain stable bodily functioning or equilibrium. As the environment presents the organism with various challenges, the body must respond to each new situation by adjusting various physiological systems to compensate for the resources being taxed. When an organism ingests a large amount of water, the kidney releases more waste fluid into the bladder for eventual disposal in an effort to maintain bodily equilibrium. They contend that failure of the body to respond to environmental challenges by maintaining bodily homeostasis results in damage to target organs and eventually death. [5], argue that catastrophes which include accidents, violent physical attacks and sexual assaults often continue to affect their victims' mental health long after the event has ended. Major life changes especially among adults, constitute the most stressful events and include death of a spouse or family member, divorce, imprisonment, losing one's job and major personal disability or illness. Work is generally considered to be beneficial to mental health. It can provide people with a sense of identity, opportunities to develop and use skills, form social relationships, and increase their feelings of self worth. Prolonged or repeated exposure to work-related stress or even a single serious occurrence can cause adverse health effects and reduce a person's capacity to perform at work.

Work-related stress is a health and safety hazard that can have negative effects on both the individual and the organisation. Causes of work stress have been linked to the work itself. Increasing demands, less freedom to control one's work, and also to the person, e.g. insufficient capacity to cope with time pressures may lead employees to experience stress. Nonetheless, many commentaries of stress in the police force in Kenya have attributed it to pay levels or morale occasioned by the poor pay they receive. [3], observes that police officers are generally never paid nearly what they should be. [6]), has shown financial problems is one of the main contributing factors towards suicide among police in South Africa. Salary increases have not been sufficient because there are other increases, including medical aid, high food prices, pension contributions and taxes that go into the total pay. In addition, he notes that promotions, deployment, transfers and good housing are considered a source of concern to officers of middle or lower ranks. These according to [6], have led to the notion that senior officers in the higher echelons may be more concerned with their own welfare, while officials at the grassroots and middle level management have to contend with pressure from all sides.

Furthermore [3], asserts that police work is not a job, but a calling. A police officer faces physical dangers on daily basis and stress for which he or she is not trained to deal with. They argue that stress could be attributed to the conflicting nature of a police officials work. The police officer is expected to be faster, changing his/her emotions than a chameleon. In the face of danger, they have to make critical life and death decision on the spur, have to face danger rather than escape, be the peacemaker and arbitrator. [7], adds that the officer is expected to accomplish a mood swing to loving husband or wife, understanding parent, school supporter and community volunteer. The study points out that in addition to the daily grind; officers are frequently the target of criticism and complaints by citizens, media, the judicial system, adversarial attorneys, social service personnel, their own administrators and other law enforcement agencies. In some cases, traumatic critical incidents can precipitate the development of a full scale post traumatic stress disorders. [8], while exploring suicide ideation on police officers found possible correlates associated with such ideation, primarily focusing on psychologically traumatic police work experiences, the development of posttraumatic stress in officers and the inordinate use of alcohol associated with this condition. [9], found that police from minority groups such as ageing police officers have been reported to experience greater stress. He also observed that sources of stress in the police force are found both in weariness of the job and private life planning.

II. Statement of the Problem

Work-related stress is a health and safety hazard that can have negative effects on both the individual and the organisation. Causes of work stress have been linked to the work itself. Increasing demands, less freedom to control one's work, and also to the person, for example insufficient capacity to cope with time pressures may lead employees to experience stress. Nonetheless, many commentaries of stress in the police force in Kenya have attributed it to pay levels or morale occasioned by the poor pay they receive. When demands exceed one's abilities and knowledge, but one is able to perceive this as an opportunity to work towards achieving a state of balance, a situation of learning and development may arise. Nonetheless, most literature reviews on work stress interventions, even very recent ones, conclude that the majority of the research on effective work stress interventions looks to individually directed interventions, which mainly aim at adapting individuals to their environment. Accordingly, employers should adopt coping strategies to assist in prevention, minimization and managing of work related stress. This study therefore sought to establish the coping strategies for work-related stress affecting performance of administration police officers in Narok County with a view to ensuring an effective work life balance thus leading to enhanced work performance.

III. Objective of the Study

The objective of the study was to establish the coping strategies for work-related stress affecting performance of administration police service in Narok County, Kenya.

IV. Literature Review

Work-related stress, has aroused growing interest in Kenya. [4], observed that the workplace has changed dramatically due to globalization of the economy, use of new information and communications technology, growing diversity in the workplace (e.g. more women, older and higher educated people, as well as increased migration), and an increased mental workload. He goes on to say that, workers are at the same time reporting an increasing level of mental health problems. In the 2000 European Working Conditions Survey, work-related stress was found to be the second most common work-related health problem across Europe. Moreover, this survey revealed that, work-related stress has also been associated with a number of other ill-health outcomes, such as cardiovascular diseases, musculoskeletal disorders or strain injuries as well as absence from work. It may thus be argued that the potential outcomes of stress at work are rather diverse, and do not only pertain to health but also to actual participation in the workforce.

According to [2], there are several key factors in the work situation that can influence the level of stress that may be experienced by employees. He observes that these factors include external environment encompassing the nature and pace of work and frequent changes in external conditions such as economy, competition, and technology. Their study, first points out those individuals who are less happy with constant change and its attendant uncertainties are likely to be stressed and the second factor in work stress is the organizational structure and culture is a factor in work stress. The jobholder's place in the job hierarchy and the extent to which individual's autonomy is encouraged or restricted are key factors in producing or avoiding stress. The dominant culture may emphasize, among others, long hours and maximum effort and may not tolerate mistakes as well as team leaders may not be supportive. It further argues that, the job characteristics - the way a job is put together, can often cause stress e.g. where conflicting tasks are present or where too much is asked of the individual; jobs that allow little personal discretion tend to increase the potential for stress. Hand in hand with the characteristics of the job are the quality of working relationships with ones superior and colleagues can have a great influence on the relative levels of stress in a job; harassment is a frequent cause of stress at work. Lastly, he argues that personal factors play a dominant role in work related stress because every individual's ability to cope adequately with pressure is greatly influenced by personal attributes such as temperament, level of commitment to the job, particular skills and talents.

A study by [7], observed that police work tends to impose a higher degree of stress and a multiplicity of stressful situations on the individual than do most other professions. The study further adds that studies have shown that those in law enforcement experience a higher rate of suicide than the national norm in America. This can be considered true in the Kenyan context where a high number of administration police officers have committed suicide mostly using their own guns. They pointed out that law enforcement has traditionally been referred to as an occupation that leads to a variety of stress related maladies such as hypertension, cardiovascular irregularities and gastro intestinal disorders. However, they noted that not all stress is bad, as limited amounts of stress can have positive results e.g. the tension of competition drives participants to excel and often enhances their performance. Chronic stress if left unchecked can have negative impact on the organization. Work is generally considered to be beneficial to mental health. It can provide people with a sense of identity, opportunities to develop and use skills, form social relationships, and increase their feelings of self worth. Prolonged or repeated exposure to work-related stress or even a single serious occurrence can cause adverse health effects and reduce a person's capacity to perform at work.

Work-related stress is a health and safety hazard that can have negative effects on both the individual and the organisation. Causes of work stress have been linked to the work itself. Increasing demands, less freedom to control one's work, and also to the person, e.g. insufficient capacity to cope with time pressures may lead employees to experience stress. Nonetheless, many commentaries of stress in the police force in Kenya have attributed it to pay levels or morale occasioned by the poor pay they receive. [3], observes that police officers are generally never paid nearly what they should be. [6], has shown financial problems is one of the main contributing factors towards suicide among police in South Africa. Salary increases have not been sufficient because there are other increases, including medical aid, high food prices, pension contributions and taxes that go into the total pay. In addition, he notes that promotions, deployment, transfers and good housing are considered a source of concern to officers of middle or lower ranks. These

according to [6], have led to the notion that senior officers in the higher echelons may be more concerned with their own welfare, while officials at the grassroots and middle level management have to contend with pressure from all sides.

A study by [8], while exploring suicide ideation on police officers found possible correlates associated with such ideation, primarily focusing on psychologically traumatic police work experiences, the development of posttraumatic stress in officers and the inordinate use of alcohol associated with this condition. [9], found that police from minority groups such as ageing police officers have been reported to experience greater stress. [10], reports that peer support component of law enforcement and other emergency services agencies has contributed to an increase in professional mental health referrals and a decrease in on-the job suicides, sick days and poor work performance. Work-related stress is a health and safety hazard with far-reaching implications for individuals and organisations alike. Identifying the causes of stress in the workplace helps in the process of assessing and controlling the hazards and risks because work-related stress can arise from a number of interrelated factors, all factors present at the workplace should be considered. Nonetheless, most literature reviews on work stress interventions, even very recent ones, conclude that the majority of the research on effective work stress interventions looks to individually directed interventions, which mainly aim at adapting individuals to their environment. Employers should thus adopt coping strategies to assist in prevention and managing of work related stress.

V. Research Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey design. The design was chosen since no attempt was made to change behavior or conditions which were measured as they were. The design has the advantage of allowing measurement of the frequency of several factors, the size of the problem and also includes analytical work to compare the factors. The study targeted 589 administrations police officers. A sample of 145 was obtained. The researcher used proportionate stratified random sampling technique to select respondents for this study. This technique was important because it assured representation of the population in the subgroups and it enhanced greater statistical precision. The study used a standard structured questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. Data collection instruments were sent by mail with introduction letters. Mailing was adopted because it is easy to administer; it's not costly and has greater degree of anonymity. Data collected was coded and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The Statistical package for Social Sciences software was used to aid the researcher in data analysis. Descriptive statistics such as cross tabulation were used to establish the mean differences in causes, prevalence and effects on performance. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was used to determine the strength and direction of associations between the variables. Chi Square test was used to show statistical significance. Trends established in the analysis were presented in tables.

VI. Research Findings And Discussions

The study found that personal sphere sources of work-related stress were prevalent meaning much more is needed to ensure personal well being of Administration Police officers in Narok County. Cumulative percentage was used to show the strength of the sources of work related stress. It was found that cumulatively, 15(10.7%) of the respondents often got stressed while struggling to make decisions, 4(2.8%) when worried about their health, 5(3.6%) when they suffered low self esteem, 15(10.7%) when burdened with unresolved past issues, 5(3.5%) when they suffered from depression, 21(15.0%) when they were unmotivated to take up challenges and 30(21.4%) when they struggled to adapt to a new lifestyle. It follows that struggling to adapt to new lifestyles 30(21.4%) tends to be the leading source of personal sphere stress followed by lack of motivation to take up challenges at 21(15.0%). Further, struggling to make decisions and burden of unresolved past issues were also significant sources of personal sphere stress. However, the least source of work related stress appears to be from worries about health 4(2.8%).

Table 1: Personal Sphere Sources of Stress

	Very often	Often	Moderately	Slightly	Not at all
Struggle to make decisions	3(2.1%)	12(8.6%)	14 (10.0%)	29(20.7%)	82(58.6%)
Worried about health	2(1.4%)	2(1.4%)	16(11.5%)	21(15.0%)	99(70.7%)
Suffer low self esteem	0(0.0%)	5 (3.6%)	10 (7.1%)	22(15.7%)	103(73.6%)
Burdened with unresolved past issues	6 (4.3%)	9 (6.4%)	11 (7.9%)	29 (20.7%)	85 (60.7%)
Suffer from depression	3(2.1%)	2(1.4%)	9(6.4%)	22 (15.7%)	104 (74.3%)
Unmotivated to take up challenges	11(7.9%)	10(7.1%)	10(7.1%)	32(22.9%)	77(55.0%)
Struggle to adapt to new lifestyle	13(9.3%)	17(12.1%)	20(14.3%)	44(31.4%)	46(32.9%)

From the results of this study, although interpersonal sphere sources of work-related stress were of lower magnitude than the personal sphere sources, they were also significantly reported among respondents. While 28(20%) of the respondents moderately got stress from perfectionist attitudes in expectations, cumulative percentage revealed that 15(10.7%) (Slightly over half of these respondents) regularly got stress from the above source. Further, 10(7.2%) of the respondents cumulatively got stress from difficulty to control anger, 6.4% from difficulty to communicate while the least 1(0.7%) regularly got stress from loss of interest in others. Further, 5(3.5%) of the respondents said they got stressed when they felt misused by seniors. From the general view of these findings, interpersonal sphere sources of work related stress tend to be slightly observed among administration police officers in Narok County. On the sources of stress in the work sphere dissatisfaction with salary, carrying out extra responsibilities and a perfectionist in duty execution ranked as the main three sources of stress cumulatively reported as often among 61(43.5%), 33(23.5%) and 38(27.1%) respectively. On the other hand, 22(15.7%) of the respondents got work sphere stress when they had to tolerate a lot of frustrating work hours 23(16.4%). Other work sphere sources of stress were no control over the work schedule while struggling to meet deadlines followed closely 18(13.1%) and struggling to get along with superiors, subordinates and peers 18(13.1%). The least source in this sphere was feeling overloaded with work 17(12.1%). Recreational sphere appeared to be a strong source of stress. On this sphere, the leading source of stress was having free time but no activities to fill the free time 33(23.5%) with 17(12.1%) (Almost half of these) very often reported by respondents. Having to tolerate frustrating long working hours was second 23(16.4%) while struggle to get along with colleagues and peers was third 19(13.7%). Not having what to do constructively in their free time and spending free time drinking or taking drugs were also significant sources of stress.

6.1 Coping Strategies

The study found that delegation of responsibilities and taking refuge in family friends were the leading options of coping with stress among APs in Narok County at (21.4% respectively). Cumulatively, 12.1% of the respondents visit the chaplain often to cope with work related stressful situations. Another 10.7% of the respondents were exercising regularly and maintaining a sense of humor respectively as the main ways of coping of with stress. Going to church, limited taking of alcohol, meditating, smoking, eating more sensibly, getting a massage and using other drugs were other ways adopted by officers to cope with stress

Table 2: Individual Coping Strategies

	Very often	Often	Moderately	Slightly	Not at all
Maintain a sense of humor	3(2.10%)	12(8.60%)	14 (10.00%)	29(20.70%)	82(58.60%)
Meditate	2(1.40%)	2(1.40%)	16(11.50%)	21(15.0%)	99(70.70%)
Get a massage	0(0.00%)	5 (3.60%)	10 (7.1%)	22(15.70%)	103(73.60%)
Exercise regularly	6 (4.30%)	9 (6.40%)	11 (7.9%)	29 (20.70%)	85 (60.70%)
Eat more sensibly	3(2.10%)	2(1.40%)	9(6.40%)	22 (15.70%)	104 (74.3%)
Limit alcohol intake	11(7.90%)	10(7.1%)	10(7.1%)	32(22.90%)	77(55.0%)
Take refuge in family friends	13(9.30%)	17(12.1%)	20(14.30%)	44(31.4%)	46(32.90%)
Delegate responsibility	13(9.30%)	17(12.1%)	20(14.30%)	44(31.4%)	46(32.90%)
Go to church	3(2.10%)	2(1.40%)	9(6.40%)	22 (15.70%)	104 (74.30%)
Visit chaplain	7(5.0%)	10(7.10%)	11(7.90%)	53(37.90%)	59(42.10%)

From the findings of the study, the leading coping strategy often used was provision of leave/ pass leave as reported by 21.4% of the respondents. This was followed closely by disciplinary mechanisms (orderly room proceedings) and hospitalization for chronic stress cases (15.0% respectively). Deployment of chaplains, AP welfare organizations, delegation of responsibilities and supervisory and commanders trainings were equally reported by 10.7% of the respondents respectively. Further, another 3.6% of the respondents reported peer group discussions and salaries and allowances improvement respectively while clear command structure and provision of equipment were reported by 3.5% of respondents each. However, conducting team-up parades (daily fitness inspection meetings) and recruitment of fresh recruits were least practiced organizational coping strategies. The respondents indicated merit in promotions, fair uniform distribution, improving police equipment, balancing of ethnic distribution, improving the welfare of officers, introduction of other courses such as leadership and computer studies, increasing salaries, building more houses, accessibility to basic information, guidance and counseling to officer affected by trauma and drugs, better vehicles, adding more resources to the chaplaincy department, payment of allowances without corruption and fairness on

transfers. The respondents also indicated the need for officers to be allowed to live outside staff quarters, establishment of recreational facilities, encouraging cooperation within the command structure, discouraging the interference of the upper command on the junior's work and an increase in remuneration as necessary organizational measures of enhancing coping ways with work related stress. The Chi square test indicated a strong association between effects of stress and the individual coping strategies such as maintaining a sense of humor, meditating, getting a massage, exercising regularly, eating more sensibly, limiting alcohol intake, taking refuge in family friends, delegation of responsibilities, quitting, going to church and visiting a chaplain

1.2 Discussions

Just as [6] noted that financial problems is one of the main contributing factors towards suicide among police in South Africa, this study also found personal sphere sources of work related stress including financial problems were significantly reported. Cumulatively, 10.7% of the respondent's often got stressed when struggling to make decisions, 2.8% when worried about health while 3.6% when they suffered low self esteem. Further, 10.7% got stressed when burdened with unresolved past issues, 3.5% when they suffered from depression, 15.0% when they were unmotivated to take up challenges and 21.4% when they struggled to adapt to a new lifestyle. These findings gel with the observation by [2] when he noted that personal factors play a dominant role in work related stress because every individual's ability to cope adequately with pressure is greatly influenced by personal attributes. It was further observed that salary increases were not sufficient because there are other increases, including medical aid, high food prices, pension contributions and taxes that go into the total pay of the officers. These findings concurred with [6], in that personal sphere sources of work related stress are not only of importance to the individual, but also reflect negatively on the organizational performance of the service. For example, having to adapt to a new lifestyle was ranked as the main cause of stress, followed by lack of motivation to take up challenges, being worried about health and low self-esteem. These could be true since the officers like other law enforcement agencies in Kenya have always complained of earning low salaries, in comparison to the armed forces. The officers tend to struggle to achieve a better lifestyle forgetting their limitations of the pay and this ends up leaving them with financial problems. At the end, these officers become stressed up and fail to either reach work places, have conflicts with colleagues and impact negatively on their performance.

In the work sphere, dissatisfaction with salary, carrying a lot of responsibilities and a perfectionist needs in duty execution were the main three sources of stress cumulatively reported as often among 43.5%, 23.5% and 27.1% respectively. On the other hand, 15.7% of the respondents got work sphere stress when they had to tolerate a lot of frustrating work hours (16.4%). Looking at these findings closely reveals relationships just like those discovered by [2]. For example, [2] found that where conflicting tasks are present or where too much is asked of the individual and jobs that allow little personal discretion increase the potential for stress. Such issues are common in the police force since the junior officers are expected to respect their seniors' commands regardless of the nature or volumes of work given to them. Further, these findings mean more interventions are warranted to enable a rational work allocations and welfare issues as a way of alleviating and addressing stress sources for the police officers not only in Narok County but also in the entire nation. The study found that recreational sphere was a strong source of work related stress. The leading source of stress was having free time but no activities to fill the free time (23.5%). Further, having to tolerate frustrating long working hours was second. Other respondents significantly reported not having what to do constructively in their free time and spending free time drinking or taking drugs were also significant sources of stress. This, as the saying goes "*An idle mind is the devil's workshop*", reveals that some of the officers may be getting stressed by being idle. Most of the respondents indicated need to have tailor made activities to keep them busy since by the time of this study, the stations did not have games such as volleyball, football or even table tennis, just to mention a few, to keep them busy. To have the greatest impact stress risk reduction, this study also found the need for intervention services to be part of an integrated program within the department and have full administrative commitment and support.

The study also established that sporting activities and other interactive ways have not been integral components of stress risk reduction among Administration police officers. These could be the solution to the rising cases of violent actions, suicide, criminal activities and lack of commitment to work among officers as argued by [2]. [1], on the other hand argues that when demands exceed one's abilities and knowledge, but one is able to perceive this as an opportunity to work towards achieving a state of balance, a situation of learning and development may arise. This according to this study is coping. The coping strategies adopted by administration police officers in managing stress include taking refuge in family and friends, going to church, exercising regularly, delegating responsibility, taking alcohol, maintaining a sense of humor, limiting alcohol, meditating, smoking, eating more sensibly, and relaxation through a massage

session. However, some of these, as revealed by this study are contradictory and are out of the norm. Coping strategies reported by respondents such as taking alcohol in times of stress are in fact stressors themselves. When such officers get drunk, their reasoning capacities are altered and formulate ambiguous solutions to the problems at hand at times leading to violent responses and suicidal attempts. The study found that there was a significant positive relationship ($R=0.542$) between the effects of work related stress and the administration police organizational coping strategies for work related stress. It follows that coping strategies at the organizational level were significant predictors of the effects and outcomes of work related stress on the organization. This means that the way an organization copes with work related stress is a determinant of the effects of the stress both to the individual administration police officer and the administration police organization at large. It is such associations between coping and effects of work related stress that warrants interventions suggested by the World Health Organization that employers should adopt strategies to assist in prevention and managing of work related stress. Prevention will help reduce risk factors through active and interactive participatory approaches to stress management. However, the findings revealed that, despite the coping strategies often used in the administration police organization such as provision of leave/ pass leave as reported by 21.4% of the respondents, disciplinary mechanisms and hospitalization for chronic stress cases (15.0% respectively), the occurrence of work related stress was still high. It can be concluded thus from these findings that the coping strategies currently in place in the AP force are not adequate to prevent and manage effects of work related stress.

VII. Conclusions

The study concluded that the causes of work related stress fall under the personal sphere; interpersonal sphere, recreational and work sphere. Officers seem to be struggling to adapt to new lifestyles and this may be attributed to frequent transfers with no defined criteria. Dissatisfaction with salary also was prominent and may be as a result of poor individual financial management skills. There currently does not appear to any existing organizational mechanism for the Administration Police service to profile these causes, prioritizing them for proactive interventions that would assist in prevention, early detection and management of these sources. As such, there is need for the service to come up with an elaborate capacity building framework for the senior officers in command to impart skills to them on early detection of work related stress, effects, best way to cope in such instances and how to reduce both individual and organizational sources of stress. The service also needs to enhance coping measures by introducing sports and other recreational activities within the administration police lines such as darts, volleyball and table tennis to ensure that off duty officers are engaged and to avoid them having free time with no activities. The organizational mechanisms in place to assist officers cope with stress appear to be inadequate and from the findings have left them to their own devices. No formal counseling is in place at the district level and the chaplains deployed seem to have assumed this role though they may not have the desired competency. Sporting activities are also non-existent in most of the AP lines and where they exist, are more of individual initiatives of Officers than official policy. The service should consider deploying fulltime counselors at least in every County to assist officers cope and manage work related stress. Currently, the chaplains deployed double up as counselors but have not enjoyed confidence from the officers. The service also needs to enhance coping measures by introducing sports and other recreational activities within the administration police lines such as darts, volleyball and table tennis to ensure that off duty officers are engaged and to avoid them having free time with no activities.

References

- [1.] J. Barling, et al (ed.), *The Handbook of Work Stress* (California: Sage, 2004).
- [2.] P. A. Collins & A. C. Gibbs, *Stress in Police Officers: a Study of the Origins, Prevalence and Severity of Stress-related Symptoms Within a County Police Force*. *Occupational Medicine*, 53, 2003, 256-64.
- [3.] K. Geldenhuys, *Super Humans-Ordinary Humans*. *Servoamus*, 96(4), 2003,9-10.
- [4.] M. A. J. Kompier & T. S. Kristensen, *Organisational Work Stress Interventions in a Theoretical, Methodological and Practical Context*, in Dunham, J. (ed.), *Stress in the Workplace: Past, Present and Future*, London, Whurr Publishers, 2001, 164-190.
- [5.] B. Green, *Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder in U.K. Police Officers*. *Current Medical Research and Opinion*, 20,2004, 101- 105.
- [6.] P. Roosendaal , *Saps Officials-Victims of Crime. The End result..... Suicide*. *Servoamus*, 95 (8), 2002, 20-23.

- [7.] L. Colwell, Stress a Major Enemy of Law Enforcement; Professionals, *FBI LAW Enforcement Bulletin*, 57 (2), 1998, 11-14.
- [8.] J. M. Violanti, Predictor of Police Suicide Ideation, Suicide and Life Threatening Behavior. *Behavior*; 34,2004, 277-83.
- [9.] F. Deschamps, I. Paganon-Badinier & A. C. Marchand, Sources and Assessment of Occupational Stress in the Police. *Journal of Occupational Health*.45, 2003, 358-364
- [10.] R. L. Levenson & L. A. Dwyer, Peer Support in Law Enforcement; Past, Present and Future. *International Journal of Emerging Mental Health*, 5, 2003, 147-152.
- [11.] J. Nyakango, *Status of Occupational Health and Safety in Kenya*. Workshop on the Safety Training Program, Beijing, China.
- [12.] W. Anderson, D. Swenson & D. Clay, *Stress Management for Law Enforcement Officers* (Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall, 1995).
- [13.] S. Palmer, C. Cooper, & A. Thomas, A Revised Model of Organizational Stress for Use Within Stress Prevention/Management and Wellbeing Programs. *International Journal of Health Promotion and Education*; 41(2), 2003, 57-58.
- [14.] M. Saunders, P. Lewis & A. Thornhill, *Research Methods for Business Students* (Edinburgh Gate: Pearson Education Limited, 2009).